

Conference Abstract

What a peaty contribution to global warming! An interdisciplinary study of atmospheric and hydrologic carbon fluxes in a temperate peatland in the Jura Mountains, eastern France

Noémie Poteaux^{‡,§}, Alexandre Lhosmot[‡], Marc Steinmann[‡], Adrien Jacotot[¶], Philippe Binet[#], Sarah Coffinet[□], Eliot Chatton[«], Camille Bouchez[«], Robin Calisti[¶], Edward Mitchell[»], Daniel Gilbert[^], Anne Boetsch[‡], Marie-Laure toussaint[^], Lilian Joly[∨], Laurent Longuevergne[!], Vincent Milesi[?], Marie-Noëlle Pons[§], Nicolas Dumélie[∨], Christophe Loup[©], Jean-Louis Bonne[∨], Delphine Combaz[∨], Virginie Girard[‡], Guillaume Bertrand[^]

‡ Chrono-Environnement, Marie and Louis Pasteur University, Besançon, France

§ Université François Rabelais, Tours, France

¶ Département de géographie, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Canada

¶ Carboflux, Saint-Denis-de-Gastines, France

Chrono-Environnement, Marie and Louis Pasteur Environnement, Montbéliard, France

□ Laboratoire ECOBIO, Université de Rennes, Rennes, France

« Géosciences Rennes, Université de Rennes, Rennes, France

» Laboratoire de Biodiversité du Sol, Université de Neuchâtel, Neuchâtel, Switzerland

^ Chrono-Environnement, Marie and Louis Pasteur University, Montbéliard, France

∨ Groupe de Spectrométrie Moléculaire et Atmosphérique, Université de Reims, Reims, France

! Géosciences Rennes, University of Rennes, Rennes, France

? Institute des Sciences de Terre d'Orléans, Orléans, France

§ Laboratoire des sciences du génie chimique, Université de Lorraine, Nancy, France

© Chrono-Environnement, Marie and Louis Pasteur Environnement, Besançon, France

‡ Observatoire des Sciences de l'Univers de Grenoble, Université Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France

Corresponding author: Noémie Poteaux (noemie.poteaux@etu.univ-tours.fr), Guillaume Bertrand (guillaume.bertrand2@univ-fcomte.fr)

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Abstract

Peatlands, though covering only 3 % of the global land surface, play an active role in the Critical Zone (CZ) by mediating substantial water and carbon exchanges with adjacent aquifers, surface waters, and the atmosphere. These ecosystems provide key services, such as carbon and water storage and local climate regulation, addressing contemporary challenges related to climate change, biodiversity loss, and water resource management. However, peatlands are increasingly threatened by global pressures, including climate change, and local disturbances, such as drainage for agriculture, forestry, and peat extraction. To mitigate these threats, it is essential to understand the hydrological, biogeochemical, and ecological processes governing peatland dynamics across spatiotemporal scales.

To explore the factors controlling greenhouse gases sources, production, and transport in peatlands, an interdisciplinary field campaign was conducted at the Frasne peatland (7 ha, 46.826°N, 6.1754°E, 840 m a.s.l.), a long-term observatory since 2008. The site is part of the French CZ research infrastructure (OZCAR) and the long term ecological research site Jurassian Arc, which focuses on the interaction between human and nature. The campaign was supported by the TERRA FORMA project, which develops smart, connected, low-cost, and low-impact environmental sensors to monitor CZ trajectories in the Anthropocene.

The fieldwork integrated microbiological analyses of peat material, including membrane lipid profiling to trace microbial metabolisms, combined with detailed hydrogeochemical investigations of peat pore water along lateral flow and depth gradients. Measurements included physicochemical parameters (temperature, electrical conductivity, pH) and major elements, dissolved organic and inorganic carbon (DOC and DIC), CO₂, and CH₄ concentration, as well as their isotopic characterization ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$). Additionally, greenhouse gases fluxes were quantified at multiple scales, employing methods such as dissolved gas profiling, chamber measurements, eddy covariance, and UAV-based surveys.

This multiscale approach aims to tackle critical challenges in peatland research and management, including

1. three-dimensional quantification of carbon fluxes (lateral and vertical) at the ecosystem scale;
2. characterization of hydrological, biogeochemical, and ecological processes that modulate greenhouse gases and dissolved carbon production and transport; and
3. development of accessible and efficient tools for addressing these pressing environmental issues.

Keywords

Isotopes, Dissolved Organic Carbon, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, Carbon-13

Presenting author

Noémie Poteaux

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.